

ASECAP DAYS

COSTA NAVARINO 2019

Parallel session 2: European Projects Presentation

Self-explaining and forgiving road infrastructure: the SAFE STRIP project

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Abstract of the presentation

When it comes to road traffic incidents and accidents, statistics show that driver inattention/ lack of reaction time/inexperience is the most usual cause. Hence, providing sufficient information to the driver about the road and traffic conditions that prevail in the road ahead is considered a major improvement in the level of road safety. Cooperative Intelligent Transportation Systems (C-ITS) may have a great impact on road safety, but their extremely small penetration rate (<10%) practically nullifies their impact. One of the main reasons behind this fact is pricing and the very high cost of applying the V2I/I2V infrastructure required in many cases for cooperative applications. In addition, further to driver attention and timely information, critical infrastructure situations (such as night-time driving and bad weather conditions, no information regarding road surface condition, etc.) also play an important role in road accidents. Bad weather conditions generally increase accident frequency (although they do not seem to have a consistent effect on severity). However, in the case of PTW (Powered Two Wheelers), roadway contamination (water, ice, snow) has an adverse effect in PTW handling and braking capabilities, resulting in more severe accidents. The condition of the road surface (surface deterioration or damaged bitumen, broken or separated asphalt, etc.) also plays a major role in the occurrence of road traffic incidents. Thus, road conditions and wear should be clearly considered in road safety systems. The purpose of the presentation is to show the progress made in the SAFE STRIP research project (H2020) regarding all the aforementioned issues. SAFE STRIP aims to introduce a technology that will achieve to embed C-ITS applications in existing road infrastructure, including novel I2V (Infrastructure to Vehicle) and V2I (Vehicle to Infrastructure), as well as VMS (Variable Message Sign)/VSL (Variable Speed Limit) functions into low-cost, integrated strips on the road; to make roads self-explanatory (with personalised in-vehicle messages) and forgiving (due to advanced cooperative functions) for all road users (trucks, cars and vulnerable road users, such as PTW's riders) and all vehicle generations (non-equipped, C-ITS equipped, autonomous), with reduced maintenance cost, full recyclability and added value services, as well as supporting real-time predictive road maintenance functions.

ERTRAC Vision Zero - 2050

- Fatality and in particular injury figures have remained nearly constant since 2013: **25,000 road fatalities and ca. 1.4 million injuries per year.**
- As a consequence, important European safety targets are getting out of reach. Neither will road fatalities be cut by 50% in the current decade, nor is the EU likely to move close to zero fatalities by 2050.
- ERTRAC Safe Road Transport roadmap: basis for FP7 and H2020 research topics

The following graph gives an overview of road safety-related projects, which have been funded partially or fully by the EU. The corresponding analysis has been done for the period from 2011 to 2021, covering projects that have been running during the Horizon 2020 programme period from 2014 - 2020. Projects are sorted in five categories: the three Haddon categories (Road User Behaviour, Vehicle Technology and Infrastructure) extended with Vulnerable Road Users, whose modal share is increasing especially in urban areas, and a category for Roadmap & Assessment activities. Red arrows refer to FP7 projects completed in 2014 or later. Completed H2020 projects are shown with blue arrows, while green arrows indicate projects which are still running.

STRIP

Explaining and forgiving Road Interactive

novation to increase the transport system safety at modal (changes).

www.safestrip.eu

Coordinator

CERTH
CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

Technical & Innovation Manager

SAFE STRIP aim

SAFE STRIP aims to introduce a **disruptive technology** that will achieve to **embed C-ITS applications in existing road infrastructure**, including novel I2V and V2I, as well as VMS/VSL functions **into low-cost, integrated strips markers on the road;**

to **make roads self-explanatory** (with personalised in-vehicle messages) **and forgiving** (due to advanced cooperative functions) **for all road users** (trucks, cars and vulnerable road users, such as PTWs riders) **and all vehicle generations** (non-equipped, C-ITS equipped, autonomous),

with reduced maintenance cost, full recyclability and added-value services, as well as supporting real-time predictive road maintenance functions.

SAFE STRIP Applications

Cooperative Safety,
Rail crossing & work zone,
Merging/intersection

Personalised VMS/VDS and Traffic Centre Information

Interface to highway autonomous vehicles functions

Predictive road maintenance

Supportive Added Value Services (eg. toll collection,
parking booking/charging)

Friction estimation module

SAFE STRIP architecture

How does SAFE STRIP work?

Micro/nano sensors, communication & energy harvesting modules placed in **low-cost, integrated strips** on the **road pavement surface**

- Installation of a **standardised road marking material with custom profile - acrylic cold plastic** - abrasion resistant, no length, width or colour restrictions.
- **Height restriction is 10mm** for the overall encapsulated and painted strip (for majority of European roads); **3-5 mm stricter restriction for some roads.**

➔ STRIP max height: 8,5 mm

Inside the strip

- Sensors measuring temperature, gas & humidity
- Strain gauges for measuring road pavement deformation (two strain gages per lane, placed at right angle to each other)
- Switches for vehicle (& speed, direction) detection
- RFID-based system for vehicle identification – For personalisation of information!
- 6 Primary (200mAh each) and 10 secondary batteries (40mAh each) & 20 Piezo, 4 solar and 2 RF harvesters

RFID: Protocol EPCglobal Gen 2V2 (ISO 18000-63); One RFID reader per strip

Reader Module

RFID passive tags

Reader module with motherboard

RFID antenna 13x10 cm

Type and scope of collected data

Data Type

Dynamic environmental parameters (i.e. temperature, humidity, water, ice, oil, smoke)

Dynamic friction coefficient (road sensors data fusion with vehicle “intelligent” tyre info)

Passing vehicle transit time, speed and position

Static info (speed limit, curvature, asphalt characteristics, crossings, work zones)

Scope

Intelligence for in-vehicle apps

Lane-level virtual corridors for automated vehicles

Road predictive maintenance

Alternative VMS and Toll Stations

SAFE STRIP Iterative testing

CRF, FIAT 500L

CERTH, Lancia Thesis

VALEO demo car - Cruise4U

Piaggio (Beverly)

Piaggio (MP3)

CERTH, Piaggio MP3 Hybrid

CONTI test vehicle

- 4 rounds (2 of them with user trials in real-traffic)
- 7 demonstrators
- 5 test sites
 - 2 highways (A22 in Italy & Attiki Odos in Greece)

Expected Impacts

- Reduction of highway fatal accidents $\approx 5\% - 8\%$
- Reduction of fatal accidents at specific traffic scenarios (i.e. merging/intersections) $\approx 15\% - 30\%$
- Cost saving for infrastructure $\approx 50\%-95\%$
- Cost saving for driver/rider $\approx 95\% - 100\%$

******Depending on the business model & the penetration rate***

System can be extended:

- In other modes
- For other C-ITS applications
- For other conceptual contexts (i.e. SAFE STRIP in pavements)

Current progress

- In the middle of iterative implementation on all levels (infrastructure, apps & demonstrators)
- Getting prepared for the first holistic setup in our test sites to test apps with users of equipped and non-equipped vehicles (cars & PTW's) under real-life conditions – **June 2019**.
- **Our final workshop with live demo will come beginning of 2020 – Stay tuned!**

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www.safestrip.eu

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